

STAMPEDE/STRATOSPHERE STATISTICAL ANALYSIS PLAN

STAMPEDE CLINICAL TRIAL APPROVALS

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STRATOSPHERE PROTOCOL APPROVALS

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Predictive and prognostic associations with transcriptome-wide classifiers and morphological features in the docetaxel and abiraterone trials of the STAMPEDE platform protocol

MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL

2.00

Tel: +44 (0)20 7670 4798

Fax: +44 (0)20 7670 4818

Email: mrcctu.stampede@ucl.ac.uk

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Contacts

Emily Grist

Peter Dutey

Louise Brown

Gert Attard

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SIGNATURES

Name	Role	Signature	Date
Emily Grist	Clinical Research Fellow, UCL Cancer Institute	DocuSigned by: Emily Grist 27300E0052F1454...	05-Mar-2024
Gert Attard	Chair of Medical Oncology, UCL Cancer Institute	DocuSigned by: Gert Attard BD146D1ADAA64A5...	05-Mar-2024
Louise Brown	Professor in Medical Statistics, MRC CTU at UCL	DocuSigned by: Louise Brown B826E52C896F494...	05-Mar-2024
Peter Dutey	Senior Research Fellow, MRC CTU at UCL	DocuSigned by: Peter Dutey-Magni 3B92FBA4A8E54B0...	05-Mar-2024
James Proudfoot	Senior Statistician, Veracyte	DocuSigned by: James Proudfoot C04435601A784C8...	05-Mar-2024
Elai Davicioni	Medical Director, Veracyte	DocuSigned by: Elai Davicioni EE6E7B4C31B5494...	05-Mar-2024
Nick James	Professor of Prostate and Bladder Cancer Research, STAMPEDE Chief Investigator, Institute of Cancer Research	DocuSigned by: Nick James C376081600384F4...	05-Mar-2024

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1 BACKGROUND

1.1 PREAMBLE

This statistical analysis plan was developed after completion of analysis of gene expression data from patients randomised in the STAMPEDE abiraterone comparison (version 1.0, dated 21 Mar-2022). This analysis led to a number of discoveries, in summary:

1. A strong and significant association between the Decipher signature (continuous and split by median categorisation) and overall survival (OS) or metastases-free survival (MFS) in both M1 and M0 cohorts respectively,
2. A strong association between immune signatures (most notably IFN-HM) and MFS in M0 but not M1,
3. A strong association between gene expression based activation of PI3K signaling and shorter OS in M1 patients.

These results were presented in-part at ESMO 2022 and described in a pre-print [1]. In parallel with these analyses, gene expression profiling of the docetaxel comparison continued; a decision was made by the STAMPEDE translational group to combine the data from the abiraterone and docetaxel comparisons. This allowed increased power for testing unexpected findings from the abiraterone comparison. Rather than perform testing of prognostic associations in the docetaxel comparison cohort separately from the abiraterone comparison, we elected to combine them and repeat the analyses – this would provide a result with greater certainty and maximise the value of the data. A further change is the use of record linkage with death registrations to secure a greater number of death events previously missed due end of follow-up Nov 2018 and Nov 2021 for the docetaxel and abiraterone comparison trials respectively. This increases statistical power in each experiment for the primary endpoint (overall survival) and one secondary endpoint (prostate-specific cancer survival). We include details on alignment of these analyses in this SAP.

The STAMPEDE platform protocol included a number of independently-powered Phase III trials that are referred to as “comparisons” when communicating with regulators given each is covered by the same protocol number.

1.2 BACKGROUND AND RATIONALE

The survival of patients commencing long-term androgen deprivation therapy (ADT) with high-risk localised or metastatic disease is highly variable. The STAMPEDE trials, in addition to a number of other phase 3 randomised control trials, have demonstrated that treatment intensification with either an AR targeted therapy [2–7] or docetaxel chemotherapy [8–10] improves survival in patients diagnosed with advanced hormone-sensitive prostate cancer commencing long-term ADT and is now standard-of-care for patients with metastatic disease. The choice of treatment is currently dictated by which drug is available within healthcare systems and/or patient preference. More recent trial data [4,11] has suggested triple therapy with ADT in addition to both intensified AR targeted therapy and docetaxel may benefit metastatic patients (particularly those presenting with *de novo* high volume metastatic disease). It has taken longer to ascertain the benefit of treatment intensification in high-risk non-metastatic patients, largely due to this cohorts overall longer survival. A meta-analysis [3] pooling data from two randomised control phase 3 trials conducted within the STAMPEDE platform protocol demonstrated the addition of AR targeted therapy (abiraterone or enzalutamide) was associated with significantly higher rates of metastases free survival. There is insufficient evidence to suggest docetaxel administered to patients with high-risk non-metastatic disease improves outcomes [10].

Despite clinical benefit from treatment intensification observed within overall trial cohorts, we hypothesised that patients may be further stratified into molecularly-defined subgroups that demonstrate differential clinical outcome and response to treatment. A large meta-analysis of trials randomising patients to ADT versus ADT with docetaxel has demonstrated that disease burden at baseline and presentation (synchronous versus metachronous metastatic disease) impacts the clinical benefit observed with docetaxel treatments [12]. Targeting treatments more precisely to patients with advanced disease will improve patient outcomes and quality of life, as well as reduce both physical and financial toxicity.

95% of patients recruited to the STAMPEDE platform protocol consented to use of their diagnostic tissue in additional research. Molecular data generated from this has given insights into how some molecular features impact clinical outcome. We have demonstrated that the burden of genomic copy number alteration in the primary prostate tumour associates with clinical outcome irrespective of metastatic state and that gene expression signatures also associate with clinical outcome [13,14]. We will now focus on whether gene expression classifiers can predict which patients stand to benefit the most from docetaxel treatment and plan to pool cohorts of patients randomised to both docetaxel and abiraterone STAMPEDE Phase III trials to increase our power to detect differences in molecularly defined subgroups.

This analysis plan is to be reviewed in combination with the analysis plan dated 21 March 2022 that defined the gene expression analysis performed on patients randomised in the abiraterone comparison.

1.3 SUMMARY OF THE STAMPEDE TRIAL

STAMPEDE is a multi-centre, platform protocol, including a number of independently-powered randomised controlled trials (Figure 1) that recruited patients with locally advanced (M0) or metastatic (M1) prostate cancer starting long-term ADT. Eligible patients had either newly-diagnosed disease or very high-risk relapsed disease (previously treated with radical radiotherapy or surgery).

Figure 1 STAMPEDE trial arm timeline

The trial uses multi-arm, multi-stage (MAMS) methods to simultaneously assess a number of different research treatments. The trial aims to assess the effects of adding therapies to standard-of-care (SOC). Every evaluation (10 in total) was independently powered and within the platform protocol was referred to as a “research comparison” (Table 1). The trial initially started with Arms A to F. Additional research arms have been included in the trial over time. Patients in the control arm receive standard-of-care (ADT with or without local radiotherapy); the research arms have this standard combined with additional investigational treatments, except for patients allocated to the tE2 arm who receive transdermal oestradiol in place of standard hormone treatment.

Metastatic patients included in this transcriptome-wide ancillary study were recruited into STAMPEDE when the standard-of-care was ADT alone, achieved using luteinising hormone-releasing hormone (LHRH) analogues or antagonists, dual androgen blockade (DAB: long-term anti-androgens in combination with LHRH agonist) or bilateral orchidectomy according to local practice (bicalutamide for non-metastatic patients was allowed in some early versions of the protocol). This standard-of-care is also the backbone of therapy for the research arms. For patients recruited from 2016, docetaxel was added to standard-of-care.

For non-metastatic patients, standard-of-care radiotherapy (RT) was mandated for all non-metastatic and lymph node negative (N0M0) patients and encouraged for non-metastatic local lymph node positive (N+M0) patients (unless contraindicated) in combination with up to three years ADT.

A research comparison is defined by those patients allocated to the research arm, along with the corresponding contemporaneously randomised, eligible control arm patients. For the purposes of presentation, individually-powered comparisons are referred to as Phase 3 trials.

Table 1 STAMPEDE research comparisons

COMPARISON	ARMS	ELIGIBLE PATIENTS	ACCRUAL		END OF FOLLOW UP	TIME PERIOD(S)
			START DATE	END DATE		
“Zoledronic acid comparison”	A, B	All patients	05-Oct-2005	31-Mar-2013	12-Nov-2018	1-4
“Docetaxel comparison”	A, C	All patients	05-Oct-2005	31-Mar-2013	12-Nov-2018	1-4
“Celecoxib comparison”	A, D	All patients	05-Oct-2005	06-Apr-2011	12-Nov-2018	1
“Zoledronic acid + docetaxel comparison”	A, E	All patients	05-Oct-2005	31-Mar-2013	12-Nov-2018	1-4
“Zoledronic acid + celecoxib comparison”	A, F	All patients	05-Oct-2005	06-Apr-2011	12-Nov-2018	1
“Abiraterone comparison”	A, G	All patients	15-Nov-2011	17-Jan-2014	30-Nov-2021	3-5
“M1 RT comparison”	A, H	Newly-diagnosed M1 pts, no contraindication to RT	22-Jan-2013	02-Sep-2016	31-Nov-2020	4-9
“Enzalutamide + abiraterone comparison”	A, J	All patients	29-Jul-2014	31-Mar-2016	30-Nov-2021	7-9
“Metformin comparison”	A, K	Non-diabetic pts, no contraindication to metformin	05-Sep-2016	31-Mar-2023	TBD	10-TBD
“tE2 comparison”	A, L	<8wk anti-androgen use Maximum 4wk LHRH therapy No bilateral orchidectomy	20-Jun-2017	31-Mar-2023	TBD	11-TBD

1.4 BIOMARKER POPULATION: STRATOSPHERE STUDY

Retrieval of tissue blocks was initiated in May 2016 with transfer from treating hospitals to the Wales Cancer Bank. In October 2017, the Prostate Cancer UK Scientific Committee recommended funding for a Precision Medicine Award to perform molecular analyses on tissue collected from patients recruited to STAMPEDE between 2005 and 2014. In July 2018 the National Research Ethics Committee approved the following protocol covering molecular analysis of the samples: “The Stratosphere Consortium Molecular Landscape Study” (Reference: 18/LO/1235). Amendments have subsequently been approved to enable whole genome expression profiling of FFPE tissue with collaborators Veracyte (previously known as Decipher Biosciences) and for plasma-based PSA and testosterone testing. A workflow has been optimised to process the tissue for morphological, transcriptomic, and genomic analyses (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Diagram of the diagnostic block processing as part of STRATOSPHERE

1.5 JUSTIFICATION FOR GENE EXPRESSION SIGNATURE TESTING

Gene expression classifiers have shown prognostic utility in low- and intermediate-risk localised prostate cancer [15–19] but have not been clinically implemented in advanced prostate cancer. Transcriptome-wide profiling performed in the Veracyte (previously known as Decipher) clinical labs (in San Diego) is an analytically validated test that has a failure rate of $\leq 25\%$ based on prior studies with similar aged formalin-fixed and paraffin-embedded tissue samples [17,20]. The failure rate to generate next generation sequencing data from DNA is typically much higher than this. Following a pre-specified analysis plan, we tested associations with survival of 59 multi-gene expression-based classifiers from patients randomized in the STAMPEDE abiraterone trial.

1.5.1 DECIPHER CLASSIFIER

In the analysis of gene expression data from the abiraterone comparison, the Decipher score classifier was the sole signature of those tested to be strongly prognostic ($p < 2 \times 10^{-5}$) in both metastatic and high-risk localised prostate cancer and identified clinically-relevant differences in absolute benefit, especially for localised cancers [1]. Analysis in CHARTED also supports that selected transcriptomic signatures, including the Decipher score, are prognostic in metastatic patients treated with ADT or ADT with docetaxel [21]. The association of docetaxel with overall survival was observed across all Decipher score groups but the relative benefit of chemohormonal therapy appeared to vary by Decipher score group. The CHARTED trial led us to hypothesise that the absolute benefit for overall survival with addition of docetaxel to ADT was higher for men with higher decipher score.

1.5.2 LUMINAL-BASAL SUB-TYPING

The PAM50 gene expression classifier, initially developed in breast cancer patients [22–24], is prognostic in metastatic prostate cancer but more intriguingly, in a relatively small sub-group of the CHARTED trial, luminal B subtypes appeared to derive greater benefit from treatment with docetaxel and ADT as compared to basal subtypes [25]. Recently, Weiner *et al.* [26] reported on a novel prostate subtyping classifier (PSC) that similarly showed in the CHARTED cohort tumours with luminal biology and a higher proliferative index ('Luminal Proliferating', LP) improved outcomes with chemohormonal therapy as compared to hormonal therapy alone. In addition, in an ancillary sub-study of the RTOG 0521 clinical trial Phillips *et al.* [27] have examined PSC in the context of high-risk localised disease treated with standard-of-care radiation and two years of androgen suppression with or without docetaxel. This analysis also supports LP subtype tumours as deriving greater benefit from the addition of docetaxel compared to non-LP tumours.

In both STAMPEDE and CHARTED cohorts, luminal A subtypes (or alternative PSC luminal differentiated), which typically have a very good prognosis, were as anticipated much less prevalent in cohorts of advanced prostate cancer patients. The biomarker cohort of CHARTED participants was

160 and it was 183 for the RTOG 0521 cohort. Whilst hypothesis-generating, these studies have provided insufficient evidence to support prospective testing or clinical implementation. We therefore aim to provide more definitive evidence that patients classified as luminal B (or luminal proliferating) derive greater benefit from docetaxel. We calculate that despite access to tumours from ~400 metastatic patients with ~300 events, we will have insufficient power to formally test for a treatment interaction. However, we believe that together with emerging data from STAMPEDE and other cohorts (including CHAARTED, RTOG0521) we will provide the greatest possible evidence for differential treatment effect from docetaxel. This will inform on opportunities for clinical implementation and integration in future trials.

1.5.3 TRANSCRIPTOME-WIDE CLASSIFIERS OF BIOLOGICAL INTEREST

In exploratory analysis of gene expression data from patients randomised in the STAMPEDE abiraterone trial, we have found the prognostic association of a number of gene expression classifiers to differ across metastatic state (Figure 3). For example, interferon signalling alpha (IFN α _HM) showed the most statistically-significant association with worse outcome in high-risk localised disease [1]. PORTOS a gene signature associated with radiosensitivity was strongly associated with outcome in high-risk localised but not patients with metastatic disease. Gene expression signatures representative of PTEN or TP53 loss biology were significantly prognostic in metastatic but not non-metastatic disease. This suggests differential effects on outcome for distinct biological processes based on the presence or absence of metastatic disease on conventional scans at time of first presentation. We plan to confirm these observations in STAMPEDE patients randomised to docetaxel in two separate clinical trials of the STAMPEDE platform protocol (with minimal overlap of control patients). We also plan to combine gene expression data from patients randomised across abiraterone and docetaxel trials to test the associations with outcome of clinically-relevant classifiers.

Figure 3 Scatter plot of hazard ratios (adjusted by one standard deviation of signature score) and p-values resulting from prognostic testing adjusted for clinical and pathological variables of overall survival in 57 signatures (with continuous scores) in patients with (A) metastatic disease and (B) locally advanced disease. Reproduced from Parry et al. [1]

1.6 JUSTIFICATION FOR KI-67 TESTING

High proliferation is recognized as a hallmark of neoplastic growth [28,29]. The most common methodology for assessment of proliferation involves the use of antibodies directed against the Ki-67

protein, a nuclear protein involved in cell cycle regulation, heterochromatin maintenance and assembly of the peri-chromosomal layers on mitotic chromosomes. It is expressed in all phases of the cell cycle other than the G0 phase [28]. This feature has made Ki-67 a clinically important biomarker for grading multiple types of cancers, with well-established prognostic value in several studies [30–36].

The proliferation index derived from the ratio of Ki-67 expressing tumour cells over the total of tumoural cells became the most studied immunohistochemistry marker in prostate cancer needle-biopsies [37–43]. Several studies found strong correlation with Gleason score in diagnostic biopsies [38,42,44] and radical prostatectomies [45–47]; others reported significant association with disease-free survival [41,48]; post-operative biochemical relapse [44,47,49,50], distant metastasis [49,51–53] and cancer-specific death [38,39,45,46,49,51,53,54] (Table 2). Ki-67 seems to be a robust prognostic biomarker but has not yet been incorporated in to the routine histopathological report as staining protocols are not uniform and there are no established cut-off values. The role of Ki-67 as a predictive biomarker is controversial but has been explored in breast cancer in the context of neoadjuvant chemo (NAC) in ER/PR positive disease where tumours with higher Ki-67 (at least 20% Ki-67 LI) seem to respond better to NAC [55–59].

We hypothesise that in a cohort of clinically advanced prostate cancer, Ki-67 scores will refine prognostication of men starting long-term ADT predicting early biochemical failure, progression and ultimately cancer-specific death. We hypothesise high Ki-67 scores will identify a subgroup of very-high risk prostate cancers with poorer outcomes that consequently will derive more benefit from therapy intensification. Furthermore, Ki-67-scores can be tested as a predictive biomarker. We hypothesise that on account of higher mitotic rates, patients with high Ki-67 scores will derive more benefit from spindle-cell toxins like docetaxel when compared to patients with very low Ki-67.

Table 2 Published reports of the prognostic value of Ki-67 in prostate cancer

Study author	Study type	Cohort treatment	Cohort	Cohort size	Tissue type	Scoring Methodology	Proposed cut-off (%)	Main positive findings
Kammerer-Jacquet (2019)	R (UK cancer registry)	untreated	localised PC	756	core bx	M	5.0%	CSD
Wilkins et al (2018)	R (case-control study)	RTx	Localised and locally advanced PC	173	core bx	M	continuous	BCR
Lobo et al (2018)	R	untreated	General population (consecutive)	189	core bx	DIA	5.3%	OS, CSD
Tretiakova et al (2016)	R	RP	Localised and locally advanced	1004	TMA (RP)	DIA	5.0%	OS, BCR, CSD
Tollefson et al (2014)	R	RP	General population (consecutive)	451	core bx	DIA	6.0%	CSD
Fisher et al (2013)	R (TAPG)	untreated	localised PC	293	TMA (core bx)	M	10.0%	CSD
Verhoven et al (2013)	R (trial RTOG94-08)	RTx vs RTx+STADT	locally advanced PC	468	core bx	M-DIA	6.2%	CSD, DM, BCR
Antonarakis et al (2012)	P (TAX2501 phase 2)	RP+adjuvant docetaxel	localised (high risk for progression)	57	TMA (RP)	DIA	continuous	PFS
Berney et al (2009)	R (TAPG)	RP	localised PC	693	TMA (TURP)	M-DIA	5.0%	OS
Khor et al (2009)	R (RTOG)	RTx+ADT	locally advanced PC	478	core bx and TURP	M-DIA	11.3%	OS, DM, CSD
Zellweger et al (2009)	P (consecutive series)	RP	localised PC	279	core bx	M	10.0%	BCR, EPE
Pollack et al (2003)	R (RTOG92-02)	LTADT+RTx vs STADT+RTx	locally advanced PC	537	core bx and TURP	M	7.1%	CSD, DM
Li et al (2003)	R (RTOG86-10)	RTx vs RTx + STADT	locally advanced PC	108	core bx and TURP	M	7.1%	DM, OS
Cowen et al (2002)	R	RTx	General population (consecutive)	106	core bx and TURP	M	3.5%	BCR, T3-T4 stage, GS 7-10

Notes: R: retrospective; RTx: radiotherapy; RP: radical prostatectomy; STADT: short-term ADT; LTADT: long-term ADT; ADT: androgen deprivation therapy; PC: prostate cancer; core bx: core biopsy; TMA: tissue microarray; TURP: transurethral resection of the prostate; M: manual (bright-field microscopy); DIA: digital image analysis; BCR: biochemical recurrence; OS: overall survival; CSD: cancer-specific death; DM: distant metastasis; PFS: progression free survival; EPE: extra-prostatic extension; GS: Gleason score

2 STUDY METHODS

2.1 ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

STAMPEDE enrolled a broad population of participants unified by the need to start long-term ADT. All participants in STAMPEDE had to meet the following eligibility:

1. HIGH-RISK NEWLY DIAGNOSED NON-METASTATIC NODE-NEGATIVE DISEASE - Both:

- At least two of: Stage T3/4, PSA \geq 40 ng/ml or Gleason sum score 8-10
- Intention to treat with radical radiotherapy (unless there is a contra-indication; exemption can be sought in advance of consent, after discussion with MRC CTU)

OR

2. NEWLY DIAGNOSED METASTATIC OR NODE-POSITIVE DISEASE - At least one of:

- Stage T any N+ M0
- Stage T any N any M+

OR

3. PREVIOUSLY TREATED WITH RADICAL SURGERY AND/OR RADIOTHERAPY, NOW RELAPSING - At least one of:

- PSA \geq 4 ng/ml and rising with doubling time less than 6 months
- PSA \geq 20 ng/ml
- Lymph node positive
- Metastatic disease

For inclusion into the gene expression translational ancillary study, STAMPEDE participants must meet the following **inclusion criteria**:

1. Enrolled into comparisons C (docetaxel), E (docetaxel + zoledronic acid) or G (abiraterone), including their concurrently randomised controls (arm A, see Table 1)
2. Have consented to participate in additional research
3. Have tissue from the primary tumour available for analyses

Participants must **not** meet any of the following **exclusion criteria**:

4. Tissue specimen collected >14 days after STAMPEDE randomisation

Gene expression data generated by Veracyte across additional clinically relevant cohorts recruited to randomised control trials may be used as outlined in this analysis plan, including CHARTED and NRG Oncology/RTOG 0521.

2.2 RANDOMISATION

Patients were randomised centrally using a computerised algorithm developed and maintained by the CTU. Randomisation was performed using the method of minimisation over a number of clinically important stratification factors with an additional random element. These factors were:

Randomising centre	each centre
Metastases	M0 vs M1
Nodal involvement	N0 vs NX vs N+
Age at randomisation	up to 69yrs vs 70yrs and over
WHO performance status	PS=0 vs PS=1-2
Method of ADT ¹	Orchidectomy vs LHRH agonist vs LHRH antagonist vs Dual Androgen Blockade (DAB)
Regular aspirin or NSAID use at baseline	yes vs no
Radiotherapy planned ²	yes vs no

¹ Method of ADT options have changed over time, from LHRH vs orchidectomy, to then include bicalutamide, then specify LHRH agonist or antagonist and more recently exclude bicalutamide but include DAB

² "Radiotherapy planned" was added as a stratification factor at the start of recruitment to Efficacy Stage I for the "original comparisons" (Mar-2008)

When implementing the additional random element of the randomisation, an 80% probability of allocation was split between the (one or more) arms with the lowest strata totals (i.e. 80% probability of being allocated to one of the minimising arms); and the remaining 20% probability of allocation was split between the remaining (one or more) arms.

2.3 OUTCOMES

Full definitions of trial outcomes are included in Table 3. The primary endpoint in the present substudy is overall survival (OS). Failure-free survival (FFS), metastases-free survival (MFS), metastatic progression-free survival, and prostate cancer specific survival will be presented in secondary and exploratory analyses.

Table 3 Outcome measure definitions with censoring criteria

TERM	DEFINITION
Overall survival (OS)	Time from randomisation until date of death from any cause from a Death CRF (Form 12). For surviving patients, censor date 1 is used. If record linkage to Civil Registrations of Death is successful, the registered date of death is used. For surviving patients, censor date 3 is used.
Metastases-Free Survival (MFS)	Time from randomisation until first of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radiologically-confirmed distant metastases • Death from any cause For patients who have not had an event, censor date 2 is used (see below).
Failure-free Survival (FFS)	Time from randomisation until first of the following events: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biochemical failure (as defined in protocol) • Local progression • Local lymph node progression • Distant metastases • Skeletal Related Event (where confirmed disease progression) • Death from prostate cancer For patients who have not had an event, censor date 1 is used (see below). If a suspicious event is reported for any of local progression, lymph node progression, distant metastases progression this will be counted as an FFS event.

Metastatic Progression-Free Survival (MPFS)	<p>Time from randomisation until first of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Distant metastases • Skeletal-Related Event (where confirmed disease progression) • Death from prostate cancer <p>For patients who have not had an event, censor date is used (see below).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If a suspicious event is reported for distant metastases progression this will be counted as a MPFS event. <p>Censor date 1 is used.</p>
Skeletal-Related Event (SRE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bone pain requiring radiotherapy and/or surgery • Pathological fracture • Metastatic spinal cord compression <p>Censor date 1 is used.</p>
Prostate Cancer-Specific Survival (PCSS)	<p>Time from randomisation until death from prostate cancer (see below).</p> <p>For patients who have not had an event, censor date 1 is used.</p>
Death from prostate cancer	<p>An automated process assigns either PCa or non-PCa as cause of death using the following rules, based on information collected on CRFs:</p>

Rule	Cause of death
1 Primary cause of death is PCa and no secondary causes are reported; progression event prior to death; no evidence of another cancer as an SAE	PCa
2 Primary cause of death is pneumonia and secondary cause of death is PCa; progression event prior to death	PCa
3 Primary cause of death is neutropenic sepsis and secondary cause of death is PCa; progression event prior to death	PCa
4 Primary cause of death is carcinomatosis and secondary cause of death is PCa; progression event prior to death	PCa
5 Death is reported as caused by PCa treatment; progression event prior to death	PCa
8 Site reports on Death CRF (version 13.0+) that responsible consultant considers death predominantly caused by PCa or protocol research / standard-of-care treatment	PCa
6 Primary cause of death is other primary cancer, and is confirmed by SAE report	Non-PCa
7 Primary cause of death is cardiovascular disease; PCa not listed as secondary cause of death	Non-PCa
9 Site reports on Death CRF (version 13.0+) that responsible consultant considers death predominantly caused by cardiovascular disease or other condition	Non-PCa

In participants successfully linked to Civil Registrations of Deaths, a death where the underlying cause is coded as any of the following ICD10 codes will be considered a PCa death:

- C61 Malignant neoplasm of prostate
- C77 Secondary and unspecified malignant neoplasm of lymph nodes
- C78 Secondary malignant neoplasm of respiratory and digestive organs
- C79 Secondary malignant neoplasm of other and unspecified sites
- C80 Malignant neoplasm, without specification of site.

Censor date 1	<p>Date taken from the latest of the relevant variables defined below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Date of randomisation (Form 1) • BMD assessment date (scan, blood sample, urine sample) • Date of treatment cycle (as taken from the bisphosphonate, docetaxel; Forms 4, 5, 6) • Date bloods taken (as taken from the bisphosphonate Forms 4, 5) • Date of last SOC docetaxel cycle (Form 21) • Date of any treatment action (Forms 7, 7B, 7C, 7D) • Date of any tE2 treatment action for Arm L patients (Form 25) • Date of tests recorded on hormone results log for Arm L patients (Form 24) • Dates reported on the Follow-up CRF (including date of PSA tests, date of any surgical interventions, date of any SRE, date of any metabolic or cardiovascular event; Forms 7, 7A) • Date of any reported progression event (Form 8) • Date additional treatment started or stopped (Forms 8, 8A) • Date of first/last RT fraction (Form 9A) • Date of late RT toxicity assessment (Form 10) • Date HT/research treatment ended (Form 11) • SAE date (onset, resolved, recent HT or trial treatment administration, start/end date of other treatment, test date) (Form 14) • Date of palliative RT fraction (Form 19) • Date blood or saliva sample obtained as reported on the pathology form (Form 18) • Date of co-enrolment to another trial (Form 15) • Date trial participation ended (Form 20) • Date last known alive (Form 7 from Version 13.0) • Date of death (Censoring date only for outcomes other than overall survival and disease-specific survival; Form 12) <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dates from the QoL forms are no longer used as a censor date as these are completed by the patient and cannot be queried for errors. • Dates of form completion are no longer used as the CRF may have been completed retrospectively. • Any date pre-randomisation is ignored within the calculation. <p>Unusual dates which have not yet been resolved or dates after the ending of follow-up for the “abiraterone comparison” on 30-Nov-2021 will be ignored for the purposes of calculating this censor date.</p>
Censor date 2 for MFS outcome measure	<p>Date taken from the latest of the relevant variables defined below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Date of randomisation (Form 1) • Date of assessment on the Follow-up CRF (unless recorded as a missed visit; Form 7) • Date of any reported progression event (If type of progression not included as event; Form 8) <p>Unusual dates which have not yet been resolved or dates after the ending of follow-up for the “abiraterone comparison” on 30-Nov-2021 will be ignored for the purposes of calculating this censor date.</p>
Censor date 3	<p>For patients successfully linked to Civil Registrations of Deaths, a censoring date will be set as 4 weeks before the data transfer, depending on what the data provider advises.</p>

2.4 SAMPLE PROCESSING

The primary analyses described in this document will be performed on a single sample per patient. The minimum tumour cellularity for tumour-enriched area selection is 25% (with maximum benign cellularity of 15% in the selected region). To select a single sample from those with multiple tumour

expression profiles, the following hierarchical selection criteria is used (moving to the next step of the hierarchy if there are ties in the criteria among multiple samples):

1. Sample(s) with the highest primary tissue Gleason pattern based on Decipher pathology review
2. Sample(s) with the highest secondary tissue Gleason pattern based on Decipher pathology review
3. Sample(s) with the longest tumour length (mm)
4. Sample(s) with the highest microarray percent positive probes above background

2.5 KI-67 SCORING AND GLEASON SCORE ASSESSMENT

All paraffin blocks with prostate needle core biopsies received at the translational site (UCL Cancer Institute) were processed at our histopathology core facility following a pre-defined protocol. Briefly, each block was sectioned at 3µm producing one section for haematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining and 7 sequential sections for future immunohistochemical staining. Slides stained for H&E were used for assessment of tumour cellularity and re-assessment of Gleason score in keeping with up-to-date scoring methodology [60–64] (Table 4).

Sections were immunoassayed for Ki-67 using MIB-1 antibody, DAKO, Carpinteria, CA, USA, and attempted to reduce pre-analytical variables by following recommendations used in the assessment of Ki-67 in breast cancer following recommended methods and platforms [30]. Briefly, cells were scored in a semi-quantitative manner, by an expert prostatic pathologist, and the mean percentage of positive cells was estimated as the proportion of Ki-67 stained malignant nuclei over the total of malignant nuclei in the tumoural area, in a manner similar to that used in routine pathology departments for the assessment of proliferation index in other organs [30,64]. Corresponding haematoxylin and eosin slides were simultaneously reviewed. Normal tonsil was used as a positive control. This technique was designed to be robust for any pathology laboratory with experience in immunohistochemistry and has been published previously [37,39].

Table 4 Prostate Cancer Grading System (adapted from Epstein et al. [61])

Gleason Score	Grade group
GS ≤6	Grade group 1
GS 3+4=7	Grade group 2
GS 4+3=7, if (%) grade 3≥5%	Grade group 3
GS 4+4=8	Grade group 4
GS 4+3=7, if (%) grade 3<5%	
GS 3+5=8	
GS 5+3=8	
GS 4+5=9	Grade group 5
GS 5+4=9	
GS 5+5=10	

GS: Gleason score

Ki-67 cell proliferation is scored semi-quantitatively, and recorded as multiples of 0.05 and indicate confidence that the true score is greater than or equal to the nominal value (eg 0.10), but strictly less than the next multiple of 0.05 (eg 0.15). For scores below 0.05, the pathologist may occasionally be confident that the proliferation score is strictly greater than 0, but under 0.05. In this event, an

intermediate score of 0.025 will be allocated to gain one additional semi-quantitative level in the dominant category.

Ki-67 scores by core will be provided to the MRC CTU by the UCL Cancer Institute and linked to the trial data by the Statistician. Quality and consistency checks will be performed to verify that Ki-67 scores have plausible values between 0 and 1 and that eligibility criteria are met. Problems will be queried with the UCL Cancer Institute.

2.6 PATIENT COHORT

A total of 2,369 UK patients were randomised to ADT (Arm A); ADT + docetaxel (Arm C); or ADT + docetaxel + zoledronic acid (Arm E) between 5 October 2005 and 31 March 2013 [8]. The Abiraterone comparison cohort randomised 1,917 patients from November 2011 through January 2014 [65]. Some participants (n=377) randomised to arm A between November 2013 and March 2013 act as control in both the Abiraterone comparison and the Docetaxel +/- Zoledronic acid comparison.

2.7 BIOMARKERS TO BE TESTED

Our primary predictive objectives (outlined explicitly in subsequent sections of this document) will test the association between the treatment effect of docetaxel and the following biomarkers (3 gene expression signatures and 1 immunohistochemistry assessment):

- (1) **Decipher:** the commercially available Decipher test using 22 probe sets in a GLMnet model [18,66]. Decipher scores range from zero to one, with higher scores indicating a worse prognosis in localised prostate cancer [20]. Clinical Decipher test risk groups developed for localised prostate cancer are Low (<0.45), Intermediate (0.45-0.60), and High (>0.60). The Decipher signature was developed to determine the risk of metastases and therefore the majority of STAMPEDE tumours have a High risk (>0.6) Decipher score.
- (2) **PAM50:** A basal/luminal subtyping model which was originally developed in breast cancer, that has prognostic utility in breast, bladder and prostate cancer [15,23,67]. Cases are split into basal, luminal A or luminal B subtypes.
- (3) **PSC:** A recently developed prostate specific 'PAM50 version 2' model [68]. A multinomial subtyping classifier that predicts one of four cancer subtypes: basal immune (BI), basal neuroendocrine-like (BN), luminal differentiated (LD), and luminal proliferating (LP).
- (4) **Ki-67:** the semi-quantitative immunohistochemistry assessment of Ki-67 protein expression will be used as a continuous variable in the analysis.

A further 56 gene expression signatures from the Genomics Resource Information Database (GRID; ClinicalTrials.gov reference: NCT02609269) will be included in exploratory analyses and are listed in Appendix 3.

All signatures except for Decipher quantile-normalised using the subset of the Decipher GRID cohort (~132,874 samples) classified as NCCN very high risk (~2,399 samples) as the reference population.

2.8 DISEASE VOLUME ASSESSMENT

M1 patients will be sub-classified according to metastatic volume, i.e. high or low volume, as determined by the CHAARTED definition [9], where high volume disease is defined as: four or more bone metastases on bone scan, including one or more outside the vertebral bodies or pelvis, and/or visceral metastases. These data will be incorporated into the analysis where specified using a finalised

copy of the volume classification dataset saved by the MRC CTU. The methodology for this classification was described previously.

2.9 TIMING OF ANDROGEN DEPRIVATION

Androgen deprivation affects transcriptional activity, which may moderate the prognostic effect of transcriptomic or proteomic signatures. The study will conduct a sensitivity analysis excluding data points from specimens collected after start of LHRHa or anti-androgens. For this, STAMPEDE CRFs 1 (randomisation), 2 (baseline), and 7 (treatment log) will be used to determine the earliest date of exposure to androgen deprivation therapy, whether it is orchiectomy, luteinising hormone releasing hormone agonists/antagonists, and/or androgen receptor antagonists (eg bicalutamide to mitigate short-term testosterone flare or as maximum androgen blockage). The biopsy date (obtained from local pathology forms when available or from trial CRFs when not available) will be compared with the date of androgen deprivation therapy. Sensitivity analyses will be performed only on patients whose biopsy was performed at the most 1 day after orchiectomy or initiation of LHRH antagonists, or anti-androgens (bicalutamide, flutamide). Patients will be kept in the dataset if the biopsy occurred at the most 5 days after starting LHRH agonists, to take into account the longer time to castration with LHRH agonists.

2.10 TRIAL DATA LOCK AND VERIFICATION

At the time of analysis:

- The Statistician will extract from Macro a dataset of all data stored in the database. This will act as the frozen dataset. It is the responsibility of the Statistician to accurately record the date of freezing and ensure all data is retrieved.
- New data can continue to be entered onto Macro database.
- If any outstanding data queries are resolved during the analysis that relate to data in the frozen dataset (e.g. problems that are found during analysis or amended CRFs that are returned to CTU), the main Macro database should be changed under the oversight of the Trial Manager.

Data verification, consistency and range checks will have been performed at the data entry stage by the MRC CTU, as well as checks for missing data (copies can be found in the Trial Master File). Additional range, consistency and missing data checks will be performed, as appropriate, when the analysis is performed (and when the datasets for analysis are constructed). All variables will be examined for unusual, outlying, unlabelled or inconsistent values.

Given the thorough nature of our follow-up procedure we expect the issue of missing data to be relatively minimal. We anticipate high compliance with initial data collection as this is close to the time of patient registration. If any data is missing imputation will not be done. Any problems with trial data will be queried with the Trial Managers, Data Managers, or statisticians, as appropriate. If possible, data queries will be resolved, although it is accepted that due to administrative reasons and data availability a small number of problems will continue to exist. This will be minimised.

3 STATISTICAL PRINCIPLES

3.1 AIMS

This analysis aims to investigate:

- (1) the prognostic effect of 59 signatures on OS in locally advanced patients, depending on systemic treatment allocation (ADT only, ADT + abiraterone, ADT + docetaxel)
- (2) the prognostic effect of 59 signatures on OS in metastatic patients, depending on systemic treatment allocation (ADT only, ADT + abiraterone, ADT + docetaxel)
- (3) whether the prognostic effect of PORTOS and interferon alpha signatures on OS is different depending on metastatic status in patients commencing long-term ADT
- (4) whether the Decipher score predicts the efficacy of docetaxel in metastatic and locally advanced patients commencing long-term ADT
- (5) whether the efficacy of docetaxel in metastatic and locally advanced patients commencing long-term ADT is greater in luminal proliferating subtypes compared to basal immune subtypes based on the PSC signature
- (6) whether the efficacy of docetaxel in metastatic and locally advanced patients commencing long-term ADT is greater in luminal B subtypes compared to basal subtypes based on the PAM50 signature
- (7) whether the immunohistochemistry Ki-67 score predicts the efficacy of docetaxel in metastatic and locally advanced patients commencing long-term ADT.

3.2 OBJECTIVES

3.2.1 PROGNOSTIC EFFECT OF 59 GENE SIGNATURES IN THE ABIRATERONE AND DOCETAXEL TRIAL COMPARISONS

The prognostic effect of 59 gene signatures (see Appendix 3) on OS will be evaluated in 8 cohorts:

- M0 patients in all arms combined
- M0 patients allocated to arm A (ADT only)
- M0 patients allocated to arms C or E (ADT + docetaxel +/- zoledronic acid)
- M0 patients allocated to arm G (ADT + abiraterone)
- M1 patients in all arms combined
- M1 patients allocated to arm A (ADT only)
- M1 patients allocated to arms C or E (ADT + docetaxel +/- zoledronic acid)
- M1 patients allocated to arm G (ADT + abiraterone)

Univariable and multivariable Cox Proportional Hazards models will be fitted as described in section 3.3. Continuous signatures will be standardised to provide more comparable effect sizes: they will be divided by the standard deviation estimated from the complete biomarker cohort. In the event of nonproportional hazards, other transformations or dichotomisation may be considered. Bimodal signatures will be converted to a categorical variable using the median for the M1 docetaxel and abiraterone cohort as a threshold.

For Kaplan-Meier curves, continuous signatures will be split using the median for the M1 docetaxel and abiraterone cohort as a threshold.

The subset of signatures with statistically significant associations with OS at the 95% confidence level will be evaluated across secondary endpoints (see Table 3) in the following cohorts:

- M0 patients in all arms combined
- M1 patients in all arms combined.

3.2.2 PREDICTIVE EFFECT OF BASAL-LUMINAL SUBTYPING (METASTATIC DISEASE)

We will test the evidence of an interaction between luminal-basal subtyping and addition of docetaxel for metastatic prostate cancer patients in relation to OS. Comparisons AC and AE (see Table 1) will be combined into a Cox proportional hazards regression model with:

- a binary variable indicating allocation to SOC + docetaxel (+/- zoledronic acid)
- a binary variable for the basal-luminal subtype.
- covariate adjustments and hazard stratification as set out in section 3.3

PAM50 classes that have not been quantile-normalised will be associated with clinical outcome to evaluate the hypothesis-generating data from the CHARTED trial [21]. The potential utility of quantile-matched PAM50 classes is uncertain and will be associated with clinical outcome in exploratory analyses outlined in section 3.2.5.

A two-sided partial likelihood ratio test will evaluate the addition of an interaction term between the basal-luminal variable and addition of docetaxel. The hypothesis will be tested at the 5% significance level. Subgroup-specific hazard ratios and 95% confidence intervals will be reported as relative treatment effect measures.

This approach will be used to test:

1. the PAM50 classifier, where the reference category will be basal subtypes, hypothesising the luminal B subtype derives benefit. Luminal A types will be excluded given good prognosis and under-representation in advanced disease.
2. the PSC classifier, where the reference category will be basal immune, compared with luminal proliferating, hypothesising the luminal proliferating subtype derives benefit. The other two types will be excluded. The quantile-normalised PSC classifier will be used in this analysis as we seek to validate the direction of association between luminal proliferating subtypes and clinical outcome published by Weiner et al. [26] in the CHARTED trial.

Given the limited power to detect even strong effects (see appendix 2), data will be reported in greater detail provided that (a) the likelihood ratio test p-value falls below a more liberal threshold of 0.10 (10% significance level); and (b) the direction of effect matches that hypothesised in section 3.1. In that event, hazard ratios or RMST differences will also be estimated for secondary endpoints to provide a more complete characterisation of the moderation observed by basal-luminal subtypes.

3.2.3 PREDICTIVE EFFECT OF BASAL-LUMINAL SUBTYPING (LOCALISED DISEASE)

In the event the likelihood ratio test significance for PAM50 and/or PSC is below 0.1 in the STAMPEDE M1 cohort, and the direction of effect is congruent with that hypothesised in section 3.1, the same analyses will be conducted in the localised disease (M0) cohort, which is smaller and has lower statistical power (see appendix 3). We will also compare to the analysis using the same parameters performed in the phase III NRG Oncology/RTOG 0521 trial [71] and consider a meta-analysis.

3.2.4 PREDICTIVE EFFECT OF DECIPHER AND KI-67

The effect of Decipher and Ki-67 on OS cohorts will be tested in M0 and M1 cohort separately. We hypothesise that the higher the Decipher score or Ki67 score, the greater the benefit of Docetaxel. Comparisons AC and AE (see Table 1) will be combined into a Cox proportional hazards regression model with:

- a binary variable indicating allocation to SOC + docetaxel (+/- zoledronic acid)
- a continuous variable for the score
- covariate adjustments and hazard stratification as set out in section 3.3.

A two-sided partial likelihood ratio test will evaluate the addition of an interaction term between the biomarker of interest and addition of docetaxel. The hypothesis will be tested at the 5% significance level.

In addition, the predictive effect will be examined for dichotomised transformations of each factor, using the median in the metastatic subgroup (from the M1 ACEG biomarker cohort) as a threshold. Comparisons AC and AE will be combined into a Cox proportional hazards regression model with:

- a binary variable indicating allocation to SOC + docetaxel (+/- zoledronic acid)
- a binary variable for the score (\leq M1 median value; $>$ M1 median value)
- covariate adjustments and hazard stratification as set out in section 3.3.

A two-sided partial likelihood ratio test will evaluate the addition of an interaction term between the biomarker of interest and addition of docetaxel. Subgroup-specific hazard ratios for the treatment effect of docetaxel and 95% confidence intervals will be reported.

Similar estimates will be produced for secondary endpoints listed in section 2.3 if (a) the likelihood ratio test p-value falls below a more liberal threshold of 0.10 (10% significance level); and (b) the direction of effect matches that hypothesised.

3.2.5 EXPLORATORY OBJECTIVES

The overarching aim of this exploratory work is to identify novel prognostic and predictive biomarkers in advanced prostate cancer patients commencing long-term ADT. To achieve this, STAMPEDE cohorts A/C/E and A/G [1] may be combined to increase our power to detect potentially clinically meaningful transcriptome classifiers. Additional randomised control trial cohorts may be leveraged to validate discoveries as they become available or to incorporate into meta-analyses, including CHAARTED [9] and NRG RTOG 0521 [71].

Exploratory Objective 1: Determine the clinical utility of multi-modal data including additional GRID signatures, morphological features and IHC data representative of distinct biological processes in the ACE and AG cohorts. Secondary trial endpoints may be included if an association with OS is observed

Exploratory Objective 2: Test for differential treatment effect with ADT +/- docetaxel or ADT +/- abiraterone for the gene expression signatures of interest in M1 cohorts and separately in M0 cohorts

Exploratory Objective 3: Evaluate the heterogeneity in GRID signature assignment in cases where multiple tissue samples are available.

3.3 STATISTICAL MODELLING

Hypotheses will be tested in models adjusted for the following adjustment variables: age at randomization (years, continuous), WHO performance status (0 vs 1-2), regular aspirin or NSAID use (no vs yes), serum PSA (prior to start of ADT and within 6 months of randomisation, continuous, log-transformed), Gleason score as assessed by the local pathologist (≤ 6 ; 7; ≥ 8), tumour stage (T0-T2; T3; T4), nodal stage and in M1 cases metastasis volume categorisation (low volume vs high volume as per CHAARTED definition). Metastasis volume is affected by data missingness, which will be investigated. In the event evidence show data are not missing completely at random, multiple imputation with chained equations will be used to address any risk of bias. Missing Gleason scores will be imputed using the dominant category. Baseline hazards will be stratified by periods of randomisation as described in Appendix 1. Univariable and multivariable hazard ratios will be reported.

Evidence of nonproportional hazards by trial arm and signature will be assessed in a Grambsch-Therneau test and graphical inspection of Kaplan-Meier curves. In the event of nonproportional hazards, restricted mean survival time (RMST) difference will be emphasised as the main treatment effect measure. The difference in **5-year** RMSTD between categories will be estimated under a bias-corrected bootstrap, with the expectation that this difference should be positive if in patients with a score greater than the median compared to patients with a score lower than the median, in absolute terms.

3.4 SENSITIVITY ANALYSES

Sensitivity analyses will examine the robustness of findings against gene expression measurement error caused by the initiation of androgen deprivation. Primary analyses will be repeated in the subset of participants whose therapy began after collection of the biopsy specimen, and model coefficients will be compared with the main analysis to detect changes in effect sizes, such as attenuation.

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APPENDIX 1: RANDOMISATION PERIODS

Where stated, hazards in survival models will be stratified by the time periods patients were randomized to, as per earlier analyses. Time periods (see Table 5 below) are defined by trial arms opening or closing, a change to the standard-of-care, or another fundamental aspect which may affect the patient population being randomized. Due to the limited number of patients randomised during periods 4 and 6 in the analysis sample, we will collapse strata 3-4 and 6-7 for this purpose.

Table 5 STAMPEDE multi-stage periods used for hazard stratification

Time Period	Definition	Accrual Start Date	Accrual End Date	Co-Recruiting Research Arms
1	From the start of the trial up to the stopping of the celecoxib-containing research Arms D & F	05-Oct-2005	06-Apr-2011	B C D E F
2	Post-closure of Arms D & F up to the opening of the abiraterone research Arm G	06-Apr-2011	14-Nov-2011	B C E
3	Post-opening of Arm G up to the opening of the M1 radiotherapy research Arm H	15-Nov-2011	21-Jan-2013	B C E G
4 (merged into 3)	Post-opening of Arm H up to the closure of the remaining original research Arms B, C & E	22-Jan-2013	31-Mar-2013	B C E G H
5	Post-closure of Arms B, C & E up to the closure of abiraterone research Arm G	01-Apr-2013	17-Jan-2014	G H
6 (merged into 7)	Post-closure of Arm G up to the opening of the enzalutamide+abiraterone research Arm J	18-Jan-2014	28-Jul-2014	H
7	Post-opening Arm J until docetaxel becomes SOC	29-Jul-2014	15-Dec-2015	H J
8	Post-opening Arm J after docetaxel becomes SOC, until close of Arm J	16-Dec-2015	31-Mar-2016	H J

APPENDIX 2: POWER CALCULATIONS

3.5 PAM50 SIGNATURE

The first hypothesis tested as part of the primary objective is the existence of an interaction effect between luminal B (PAM50) and allocation to docetaxel in de novo metastatic patients enrolled into comparisons C or E (N=1,387). Among those, 524 patients (1) had not opted out to tissue acquisition and processing; (2) had specimens obtained and subjected to expression profiling; (3) had specimens within -270 days and +14 days of randomisation; and (4) had specimens taken before initiation of ADT. Assuming balanced allocation between control and treatment; that 85% pass quality control; and that 0% are luminal A, 39% luminal B, and 61% basal, we expect the analytical cohort to consist of:

- $524 * 0.88 * 1 = 461$ patients after exclusion of luminal A (50% allocated to ADT, 50% allocated to ADT + docetaxel +/- zoledronic acid)
- $524 * 0.88 * 0.39 = 180$ luminal B patients
- $524 * 0.88 * 0.61 = 281$ basal patients

Assuming independence between allocation to treatment and luminal/basal subtyping, and that 69% of the cohort has an all-cause death event record, estimated power for plausible effect sizes are plotted on Figure 4 below based on exponential approximation formulae by Schmoor et al. [72].

Figure 4 Power to detect a treatment effect interaction with PAM50 in the metastatic cohort allocated to ADT or ADT + docetaxel +/- zoledronic acid (ACE)

In localised disease, power was estimated for two possible endpoints: overall survival (assuming 35% of the cohort has an event) and metastases-free survival (assuming 43% of the cohort has an event), assuming 2% are luminal A, 45% luminal B, and 54% basal (Figure 5 below).

Figure 5 Power to detect a treatment effect interaction with PAM50 (luminal B vs basal) in the localised cohort allocated to ADT or ADT + docetaxel +/- zoledronic acid (ACE) by endpoint (OS vs MFS)

3.6 PSC SIGNATURE

The second hypothesis tested as part of the primary objective is the existence of an interaction effect between luminal B (PSC) and allocation to docetaxel in de novo metastatic patients enrolled into comparisons C or E. Assuming a class distribution of: 3% Luminal Differentiated (LD); 33% Luminal Proliferating (LP); 52% Basal Immune (BI); 12% Basal Neuroendocrine-Like (BN), we expect the analytical cohort to consist of:

- $524 * 0.88 * 0.85 = 392$ patients after exclusion of LD and BN (50% allocated to ADT, 50% allocated to ADT + docetaxel +/- zoledronic acid)
- $524 * 0.88 * 0.33 = 152$ LP patients
- $524 * 0.88 * 0.52 = 240$ BI patients.

Assuming independence between allocation to treatment and luminal/basal subtyping, and that 69% of the cohort has an all-cause death event record, estimated power for plausible effect sizes are plotted on Figure 6 below.

Figure 6 Power to detect a treatment effect interaction with PSC (LP vs BI) in the metastatic cohort allocated to ADT or ADT + docetaxel +/- zoledronic acid (ACE)

In localised disease, power was estimated for two possible endpoints: overall survival (assuming 35% of the cohort has an event) and metastases-free survival (assuming 43% of the cohort has an event), assuming a class distribution of: 31% Luminal Proliferating (LP) and 52% Basal Immune (BI).

Figure 7 Power to detect a treatment effect interaction with PSC (LP vs BI) in the localised cohort allocated to ADT or ADT + docetaxel +/- zoledronic acid (ACE)

3.7 KI-67 SCORE

No closed form formulae are available for the power of detecting interaction effects with continuous variables in survival analysis models, but it is possible to examine power for a binary reclassification

of Ki-67 around the median. Simulation studies have shown the power to detect treatment effect modification with dichotomised factors is severely reduced. The estimates presented below at the 5% significance level can therefore be considered to be conservative (Figure 8).

Figure 8 Statistical power for the docetaxel predictive hypothesis in metastatic patients (arms A+C) with significance level of 0.05 depending on the magnitude of the Ki-67 (\leq median) hazard ratio parameter and the choice of endpoint. Overall survival, the chosen endpoint, is compared with radiological progression-free survival.

APPENDIX 3: LIST OF GENE EXPRESSION SIGNATURES FOR PROGNOSTIC ANALYSES

abi_sens
ADT_sens
Angiogenesis
AR_HM
AR-A
ARv7
ARv7_Sharp
Basal_Zhang
Bromo10
CCP
CHD1_Liu
cholesterol_HM
chrom_instab
Decipher
EMT_HM
ERE_HM
ERG
ERL_HM
EST_Purity
EST_Stromal
FA
FA_HM
Glycolysis
GR
Hieronymus
Hieronymus_repr
HR
HRdef
Hypoxia_HM
IFN_HM
Imm190
inflammation_HM
IPS_CD4_Act
IPS_CD8_Act
IPS_CTLA4
IPS_MDSC
IPS_PDL2
IPS_Treg
KRAS_HM
Kumar
Mtorc1_HM
NE_Alshalalfa
NE_Balanis
NE_Beltran
NE_Kumar
NE_Tsai
PAM50
Persist

PI3K_HM
PORTOS
Progenesis
PSC
PTEN_Liu
PTEN_Saal
RT_sens
SPOP_Liu
TLS
TP53_1
TP53_2

Certificate Of Completion

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Subject: Complete with DocuSign: SAP_docetaxel_transcriptomics_v2.0.pdf	
Source Envelope:	
Document Pages: 34	Signatures: 7
Certificate Pages: 5	Initials: 0
AutoNav: Enabled	Envelope Originator:
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Time Zone: (UTC) Dublin, Edinburgh, Lisbon, London	90 High Holborn 2nd Floor London
	London, London WC1V 6LJ
	asiyya.tahsin.21@ucl.ac.uk
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Signer Events

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 Elai.Davicioni@veracyte.com
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James Proudfoot
 james.proudfoot@veracyte.com
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Agent Delivery Events	Status	Timestamp
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Payment Events	Status	Timestamps
Electronic Record and Signature Disclosure		

ELECTRONIC RECORD AND SIGNATURE DISCLOSURE

From time to time, MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL (we, us or Company) may be required by law to provide to you certain written notices or disclosures. Described below are the terms and conditions for providing to you such notices and disclosures electronically through the DocuSign system. Please read the information below carefully and thoroughly, and if you can access this information electronically to your satisfaction and agree to this Electronic Record and Signature Disclosure (ERSD), please confirm your agreement by selecting the check-box next to 'I agree to use electronic records and signatures' before clicking 'CONTINUE' within the DocuSign system.

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At any time, you may request from us a paper copy of any record provided or made available electronically to you by us. You will have the ability to download and print documents we send to you through the DocuSign system during and immediately after the signing session and, if you elect to create a DocuSign account, you may access the documents for a limited period of time (usually 30 days) after such documents are first sent to you. After such time, if you wish for us to send you paper copies of any such documents from our office to you, you will be charged a \$0.00 per-page fee. You may request delivery of such paper copies from us by following the procedure described below.

Withdrawing your consent

If you decide to receive notices and disclosures from us electronically, you may at any time change your mind and tell us that thereafter you want to receive required notices and disclosures only in paper format. How you must inform us of your decision to receive future notices and disclosure in paper format and withdraw your consent to receive notices and disclosures electronically is described below.

Consequences of changing your mind

If you elect to receive required notices and disclosures only in paper format, it will slow the speed at which we can complete certain steps in transactions with you and delivering services to you because we will need first to send the required notices or disclosures to you in paper format, and then wait until we receive back from you your acknowledgment of your receipt of such paper notices or disclosures. Further, you will no longer be able to use the DocuSign system to receive required notices and consents electronically from us or to sign electronically documents from us.

All notices and disclosures will be sent to you electronically

Unless you tell us otherwise in accordance with the procedures described herein, we will provide electronically to you through the DocuSign system all required notices, disclosures, authorizations, acknowledgements, and other documents that are required to be provided or made available to you during the course of our relationship with you. To reduce the chance of you inadvertently not receiving any notice or disclosure, we prefer to provide all of the required notices and disclosures to you by the same method and to the same address that you have given us. Thus, you can receive all the disclosures and notices electronically or in paper format through the paper mail delivery system. If you do not agree with this process, please let us know as described below. Please also see the paragraph immediately above that describes the consequences of your electing not to receive delivery of the notices and disclosures electronically from us.

How to contact MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL:

You may contact us to let us know of your changes as to how we may contact you electronically, to request paper copies of certain information from us, and to withdraw your prior consent to receive notices and disclosures electronically as follows:

To contact us by email send messages to: s.assam@ucl.ac.uk

To advise MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL of your new email address

To let us know of a change in your email address where we should send notices and disclosures electronically to you, you must send an email message to us at s.assam@ucl.ac.uk and in the body of such request you must state: your previous email address, your new email address. We do not require any other information from you to change your email address.

If you created a DocuSign account, you may update it with your new email address through your account preferences.

To request paper copies from MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL

To request delivery from us of paper copies of the notices and disclosures previously provided by us to you electronically, you must send us an email to s.assam@ucl.ac.uk and in the body of such request you must state your email address, full name, mailing address, and telephone number. We will bill you for any fees at that time, if any.

To withdraw your consent with MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL

To inform us that you no longer wish to receive future notices and disclosures in electronic format you may:

- i. decline to sign a document from within your signing session, and on the subsequent page, select the check-box indicating you wish to withdraw your consent, or you may;
- ii. send us an email to s.assam@ucl.ac.uk and in the body of such request you must state your email, full name, mailing address, and telephone number. We do not need any other information from you to withdraw consent.. The consequences of your withdrawing consent for online documents will be that transactions may take a longer time to process..

Required hardware and software

The minimum system requirements for using the DocuSign system may change over time. The current system requirements are found here: <https://support.docusign.com/guides/signer-guide-signing-system-requirements>.

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To confirm to us that you can access this information electronically, which will be similar to other electronic notices and disclosures that we will provide to you, please confirm that you have read this ERSD, and (i) that you are able to print on paper or electronically save this ERSD for your future reference and access; or (ii) that you are able to email this ERSD to an email address where you will be able to print on paper or save it for your future reference and access. Further, if you consent to receiving notices and disclosures exclusively in electronic format as described herein, then select the check-box next to ‘I agree to use electronic records and signatures’ before clicking ‘CONTINUE’ within the DocuSign system.

By selecting the check-box next to ‘I agree to use electronic records and signatures’, you confirm that:

- You can access and read this Electronic Record and Signature Disclosure; and
- You can print on paper this Electronic Record and Signature Disclosure, or save or send this Electronic Record and Disclosure to a location where you can print it, for future reference and access; and
- Until or unless you notify MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL as described above, you consent to receive exclusively through electronic means all notices, disclosures, authorizations, acknowledgements, and other documents that are required to be provided or made available to you by MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL during the course of your relationship with MRC Clinical Trials Unit at UCL.